

IMPROVING FUTURE PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS' COMPETENCE IN USING MEDIA LITERACY

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Abstract: In the article, a modern educational institution is responsible for forming a socially active, positive-thinking person, developing the skills and competences of students to use the flow of information correctly, mastering innovative technologies, and the task of independent learning by deepening and expanding knowledge. The problem of shifting attention from a knowledgeable approach to a competent approach is discussed in the modernization of national education.

Key words: multimedia tools, primary education, media literacy, technological tools, educational system.

Introduction:

In the socio-political, agricultural and ethnic-cultural environment of the development of Uzbekistan, the system of education in the primary class with the help of information and communication technologies, the factors of national and community requirements for the development of professional communicative competence, personal and professional is becoming a necessary part of life. Learning professional communicative competence using information and communication technologies is the basis for solid learning of skills and knowledge.

Today, the Council of Europe promotes the use of information and communication technologies as an effective tool in the development of students' professional communicative competence through knowledge of multiple languages. This means that every European should know at least two languages, and in order to be able to use one of them actively, it is necessary to know some information and communication technologies.

All higher education institutions in Uzbekistan need to improve the methodology of teaching information technology to future elementary school teachers in the new Digitization conditions. In this regard, the importance of students in education, their professional functions in the labor market as a whole, and this, in turn, led to an increase in the tendency to develop and the development of professional communicative competences by means of information and communication technologies. The education policy of each higher education institution should be aimed at solving the problem of training of competitive specialists who are socially protected, adapted to constantly changing conditions and have developed professional communicative competence.

According to I. L. Beam, it includes and means learning practical knowledge as a basis for self-regulation and self-correction through information and communication technologies. In the last 10-15 years Deep changes have occurred in the practice of teaching information and communication technologies in Uzbekistan. By expanding international relations and agricultural activities, a new level of learning was established in the primary school. In this

context, it can be said that the development of professional communicative competences of agricultural students through learning a foreign language with the help of information and communication technologies is gaining importance in their professional activities. The International Organization of the Council of Europe is entrusted with the task of helping to coordinate the goals and content of education in Asian countries by means of information and communication technologies. Uzbekistan's membership in the Council of Europe showed the need to harmonize Uzbekistan's educational standards with common European standards.

In current situations, the purpose and task of improving the methodology of teaching information technology to future elementary school teachers in the conditions of digitization for students of higher education institutions is to develop professional communicative competence of students. For this, it is very important to effectively implement the goal (*mission*) and tasks of global learning of foreign languages with the help of information and communication technologies in each higher education institution. In the initial stages of development, programs for the use of information and communication technologies in the educational process were developed, ideas about their use in the educational process were positively and critically re-examined, and methodological bases for their use in the educational process were created. In the course of the lesson, suggestions that it is possible to organize full education only from information and communication technologies without the teacher interfering with the lesson were rejected. However, information and communication technologies have not only freed teachers from the usual, traditional tasks, but also imposed tasks related to programming, teaching materials and technical coordination. For this, it was necessary to develop a system of special knowledge and skills far from pedagogy and psychology. Conceptual laws defining various educational opportunities of information and communication technologies have been developed. High-level personalization, rapid data acquisition and processing, and problem-solving capabilities of information and communication technologies were demonstrated. In his scientific works, A.R. Artyomov substantiates the scientific idea of developing professional communicative competence of students through remote teaching of audio and video materials and its computer programs.

In order for information and communication technologies to be a powerful factor in the effectiveness of the didactic process, they should correspond to the goal-content program of this process and help to implement the main functions of pedagogical management. Conditions for effective use of information and communication technologies in the educational process.

Therefore, in order to improve the teaching methodology of information technology in future elementary school teachers in the context of Digitization in the educational process, the teacher should know the right balance between technology tools, teaching methods and approaches need The most important thing is that the use of information and communication technologies in teaching develops the professional communicative competence of students, the possibility of developing research skills, intellectual competence to develop independence, creative thinking, cognitive activity, reasoning, writing essays and checking skills.

In the conditions of digitalization, the future primary class teachers were distinguished by the rapid development of research in areas where it is possible to improve the methodology of teaching information technology. Later, one of several Uzbek scientists, R. J.

Ishmuamedov, suggested that it is better to use information and communication technologies in primary classes, to perform the tasks of consultants, partners and for educational purposes.

Thus, in the conditions of digitalization, it is necessary to improve the methodology of teaching information technology to future elementary school teachers, to develop programs to support the use of information and communication technologies for teaching in elementary school, and to develop training and test programs. output, development of computer courses, distance learning, we can see that the use of the Internet in classrooms is effective.

In the conditions of digitization, it is the most suitable and effective tool for improving the teaching methodology of information technologies among future elementary school teachers, and their goal is to develop students' professional communication. It is desirable to arouse interest in the use of information and communication technologies in teaching in primary classes and to introduce them on a large scale in all higher education institutions. This is confirmed by the fact that the global network of the Internet allows teachers to solve many problems in the field of professional communication skills development.

The ability to improve the methodology of teaching information technology, develop research activities and search for information in future elementary school teachers in the conditions of digitization; is the most effective means of developing communication skills. M.K. Gulyamova emphasizes that this applies especially to the communication possibilities of the Internet for solving specific educational tasks, developing and improving certain educational skills and qualifications, and organizing educational relations. In this regard, it is important to develop such issues as communication in learning and teaching foreign languages, methods of obtaining information and audiovisual materials from the Internet, and the use of information and communication technologies in learning various subjects. In the conditions of digitization, the future primary class provides new opportunities for teachers to improve the teaching methodology of information technologies. Using the Internet allows you to conduct online classes in real time. Learning on the basis of information and communication technologies in the primary school consists in developing students' professional communicative communication, organizing lively communication and activity in computer networks.

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